

Cost-sensitive feature selection for Support Vector Machines

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Abstract

Feature Selection (FS) is a crucial procedure in Data Science tasks such as Classification, since it identifies the relevant variables, making thus the classification procedures more interpretable and more effective by reducing noise and data overfit. The relevance of features in a classification procedure is linked to the fact that misclassifications costs are frequently asymmetric, since false positive and false negative cases may have very different consequences. However, off-the-shelf FS procedures seldom take into account such cost-sensitivity of errors.

In this paper we propose a mathematical-optimization-based FS procedure embedded in one of the most popular classification procedures, namely, Support Vector Machines (SVM), accommodating asymmetric misclassification costs. The key idea is to replace the traditional margin maximization by minimizing the number of features selected, but imposing upper bounds on the false positive and negative rates. The problem is written as an integer linear problem plus a quadratic convex problem for SVM with both linear and radial kernels.

The reported numerical experience demonstrates the usefulness of the proposed FS procedure. Indeed, our results on benchmark data sets show that a

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substantial decrease of the number of features is obtained, whilst the desired trade-off between false positive and false negative rates is achieved.

Keywords: Classification, Data Science, Support Vector Machines, Feature Selection, Integer Programming, Sparsity

1. Introduction

Supervised Classification is one of the most important tasks in Data Science, e.g. [1, 2], full of challenges from a Mathematical Optimization perspective, e.g. [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17].

5 In its most basic version, we are given a set I of individuals, each represented by a vector (x_i, y_i) , where $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the so-called feature vector, and $y_i \in \mathcal{C} = \{-1, 1\}$ is the membership of individual i . A classifier Ψ , i.e., a function $\Psi : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$, is sought to assign labels $c \in \mathcal{C}$ to incoming individuals for which the feature vector x is known but the label y is unknown and estimated
10 through $\Psi(x)$.

The different classification procedures differ in the way the classifier Ψ is obtained from the data set I . A frequent approach consists of reducing the search of the classifier to the resolution of an optimization problem, see [9]. This is the case, among many others, of the state-of-the-art classifier known as
15 Support Vector Machines (SVM), [9, 18, 19, 20], addressed in this paper.

In SVM *with linear kernel*, Ψ takes the form

$$\Psi(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mathbf{w}^\top x + \beta \geq 0 \\ -1, & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$ are obtained as the optimal solution of the following convex quadratic programming formulation with linear constraints

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{w}, \beta, \xi} \quad & \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{w} + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & y_i(\mathbf{w}^\top x_i + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad i \in I \\ & \xi_i \geq 0 \quad i \in I. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here $C > 0$ is the *regularization parameter*, which needs to be tuned, and $\xi_i \geq 0$ is a penalty associated to misclassifying individual i in the so-called training sample I .

An apparently innocent extension of (1) is given by

$$\Psi(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \mathbf{w}^\top \phi(x) + \beta \geq 0 \\ -1, & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\phi : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ maps the original N features into a vector space of higher dimension, and \mathbf{w} and β are obtained by solving an optimization problem formally identical to (2), but taking place in the space \mathcal{H} instead of \mathbb{R}^N

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{w}, \beta, \xi} \quad & \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{w} + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & y_i(\mathbf{w}^\top \phi(x_i) + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad i \in I \\ & \xi_i \geq 0 \quad i \in I. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

In this case, the classifier is usually obtained by solving, instead of (4), its dual,

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\alpha} \quad & \sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i, j \in I} \alpha_i y_i \alpha_j y_j K(x_i, x_j) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i = 0 \\ & 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq \frac{C}{2}, \quad i \in I, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $K(x, x') = \phi(x)^\top \phi(x')$ is the so-called *kernel function*. From the optimal solution to (5) and taking into account the complementarity slackness conditions, \mathbf{w} and β in (3) are obtained. In particular,

$$\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{w} = \sum_{i, j \in I} \alpha_i y_i \alpha_j y_j K(x_i, x_j), \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{w}^\top \phi(x) = \sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x). \quad (7)$$

See e.g. [9, 18, 19, 20] for details.

The classifier uses all the features involved in the problem, both in (1) and (3), which may be rather problematic if the dimension N of the data set is large, since it will be hard to identify which features are significant for classification purposes. It is then advisable to perform Feature Selection (FS), [21, 22, 23,

24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30], in order to reduce the set of features and obtain an appropriate trade-off between classification accuracy and sparsity.

A mountain of different FS procedures are found in the literature, some independent of the classification procedure (FS is performed in advance, based e.g. on the correlation between each feature and the label) and others embedded in the classification procedure. The latter is the approach considered in this paper, since we aim to obtain an SVM-based classifier, and, at the same time, perform the selection of the features. The core idea is the optimization problem to be solved: instead of maximizing the margin, as in the traditional SVM, we seek the classifier with lowest number of features, but without damaging too much the original performance. In order to be able to control the classifier's performance, we will make use of constraints as in [31]. Specifically, the formulation of the constrained SVM with linear kernel is

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_{\mathbf{w}, \beta, \xi} \quad & \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{w} + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\
s.t. \quad & y_i(\mathbf{w}^\top x_i + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad i \in I \\
& 0 \leq \xi_i \leq L(1 - \zeta_i) \quad i \in I \\
& \mu(\zeta)_\ell \geq \lambda_\ell \quad \ell \in L \\
& \zeta_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad i \in I.
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

In essence, this is simply the formulation for the SVM with linear kernel, to which performance constraints ($\mu(\zeta)_\ell \geq \lambda_\ell$) have been added, see [31] for the details. Its (partial) dual formulation is

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_{\alpha, \beta, \xi, \zeta} \quad & \sum_{i, j \in I} \alpha_i y_i \alpha_j y_j K(x_i, x_j) + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\
s.t. \quad & y_i(\sum_{j \in I} \alpha_j y_j K(x_j, x_i) + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad i \in I \\
& \sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i = 0 \\
& 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C/2 \quad i \in I \\
& 0 \leq \xi_i \leq L(1 - \zeta_i) \quad i \in I \\
& \mu(\zeta)_\ell \geq \lambda_\ell \quad \ell \in L \\
& \zeta_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad i \in I.
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

As before, this is similar to the standard partial dual formulation of the SVM

with general kernel and constraints in the performance measures, as in (8). For more information about how formulation (9) is obtained, the reader is referred to the Appendix. Note that, while mathematical optimization problems addressed in the statistical literature are, traditionally, as (2) or (5), nonlinear programs in continuous variables, our approach involves integer variables, which define harder optimization problems. However, Integer Programming has shown to be rather competitive thanks to the impressive advances in (nonlinear) integer programming, as demonstrated in recent papers addressing different topics in data analysis, [32, 33, 24, 7, 8, 34].

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we present the new FS methodology for SVM, by proposing mathematical optimization programs. For either linear or nonlinear kernels, we reduce the problem to solving a standard linear integer program plus, eventually, a quadratic convex problem. Our FS approach is empirically tested. In Section 3 we describe how the different experiments have been carried out. Then, the results of those experiments are shown in Section 4. Comparisons between the use of linear and radial kernels, and between the standard linear SVM with and without embedded FS are provided. The paper ends with conclusions and possible extensions in Section 5.

2. Cost-sensitive Feature Selection

In this section we present a novel linear formulation for SVM where classification costs are modeled via certain constraints, and where, in addition, a FS approach is embedded in such a way that only the relevant features are considered. In Section 2.2 the FS approach using a linear or an arbitrary kernel is addressed.

In order to cope with classification costs, first we recall some performance measures, namely,

- TPR (True Positive Rate): $P(\mathbf{w}^\top X + \beta > 0 | Y = +1)$
- TNR (True Negative Rate): $P(\mathbf{w}^\top X + \beta < 0 | Y = -1)$

- Acc (Accuracy): $P(Y(\mathbf{w}^\top X + \beta) > 0)$.

The objective is to classify using a reduced set of features in such a way that certain constraints over the performance, such as $TPR \geq \lambda_1$ or $TNR \geq \lambda_{-1}$ (for threshold values $\lambda_1, \lambda_{-1} \in [0, 1]$), are fulfilled.

Note that the pair (X, Y) is a random vector (with unknown distribution) from which a sample $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i \in I}$ is generated. This implies that TPR and TNR are statistics and therefore, they should be estimated from sample data. This leads to the empirical constraints $\widehat{TPR} \geq \lambda_1^*$ and $\widehat{TNR} \geq \lambda_{-1}^*$, for $\lambda_1^* \geq \lambda_1$ and $\lambda_{-1}^* \geq \lambda_{-1}$, where the performance measures are replaced by their sample estimates. Two possible choices, which shall be explored in this work, are

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1^* &= \lambda_1 \\ &\text{and} \\ \lambda_{-1}^* &= \lambda_{-1}, \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

or the more conservative approach based on Hoeffding inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1^* &= \lambda_1 + \sqrt{\frac{-\log \alpha}{2|I_+|}} \\ &\text{and} \\ \lambda_{-1}^* &= \lambda_{-1} + \sqrt{\frac{-\log \alpha}{2|I_-|}}, \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where α is the significance level for the hypothesis test whose null hypothesis is either $TPR \leq \lambda_1$ or $TNR \leq \lambda_{-1}$. See [31] for more details.

Note that it is straightforward to extend our results to the case in which measurement costs are associated with the features, as in e.g. [35], and then the minimum-cost feature set is sought instead.

2.1. The cost-sensitive FS procedure

Assume that we have a linear kernel, i.e., $K(x, x') = x^\top x'$, and thus the SVM with all features is obtained by solving (2). We state the feature selection problem as a Mixed Integer Linear Program. Consider an auxiliary variable ζ_i that takes the value 1 if record i is correctly classified and is equal to 0 otherwise. Hence, estimates of TPR and TNR from sample I are given by

$\widehat{TPR} = \sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i(1+y_i)/\sum_{i \in I}(1+y_i)$ and $\widehat{TNR} = \sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i(1-y_i)/\sum_{i \in I}(1-y_i)$,
 105 respectively. Associated with each feature k , $1 \leq k \leq N$, we define the variable z_k taking the value 1 if feature k is selected for classifying, and 0 otherwise. Hence, the optimization problem that defines a linear classifier (hyperplane) taking into account the classification rates and in which a FS procedure is integrated is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{\mathbf{w}, \beta, z, \zeta} \quad & \sum_{k=1}^N z_k \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & y_i(\mathbf{w}^\top x_i + \beta) \geq 1 - L(1 - \zeta_i), \quad \forall i \in I \\
 & \sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i(1 - y_i) \geq \lambda_{-1}^* \sum_{i \in I} (1 - y_i) \\
 & \sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i(1 + y_i) \geq \lambda_1^* \sum_{i \in I} (1 + y_i) \tag{P1} \\
 & |w_k| \leq Mz_k \quad \forall k \in 1, \dots, N \\
 & \zeta_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in I \\
 & z_k \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall k \in 1, \dots, N
 \end{aligned}$$

110 where M and L are sufficiently large numbers.

Let us discuss the rationality of the formulation (P1). The number of features used for classifying is to be minimized in the objective. The first constraint identifies which individuals are correctly classified, since, as soon as $\zeta_i = 1$, the score $\Psi(x_i)$ is forced to be $\Psi(x_i) \geq 1$ (if $y_i = 1$) or $\Psi(x_i) \leq -1$ (if $y_i = -1$).
 115 Furthermore, the constant $\sum_{i \in I} (1 - y_i)$ is equal to two times the cardinality of the set $\{i \in I : y_i = -1\}$, whereas $\sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i(1 - y_i)$ yields two times the number of individuals correctly classified in the class -1 . Hence, the second and third constraints force respectively the fraction of individuals with label $y_i = -1$ (respectively, $y_i = 1$) correctly classified to be at least λ_{-1}^* (respectively, at least
 120 λ_1^*). Finally, the fourth constraint forces to select those features k with $z_k = 1$.

Note that an SVM classifier has not been built yet, since the margin has not been maximized. The next section shall address such problem by using the SVM either with the linear kernel or with an arbitrary one.

2.2. Cost-sensitive sparse SVMs: linear vs arbitrary kernels

Here we explain how the sparse SVM is built. Let us first consider the case

of the classifier with linear kernel. Hence, the sparse SVM that controls the classification rates is formulated as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\omega, \beta, \xi, z} \quad \sum_{j=1}^N w_j^2 z_j + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad y_i (\sum_{j=1}^N \omega_j z_j x_{ij} + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad \forall i \in I \\
& \quad \quad 0 \leq \xi_i \leq M(1 - \zeta_i) \quad \forall i \in I \quad (P2) \\
& \quad \quad \zeta_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in I \\
& \quad \quad \sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i (1 - y_i) \geq \lambda_{-1}^* \sum_{i \in I} (1 - y_i) \\
& \quad \quad \sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i (1 + y_i) \geq \lambda_1^* \sum_{i \in I} (1 + y_i)
\end{aligned}$$

125 Note that (P2) is defined similarly as a standard linear SVM optimization problem. The slight difference is that in (P2) only the variables selected by the FS approach described in Section 2.1. are considered. This means that the values of z in (P2) are those obtained in problem (P1). Note too that the constraints concerning the performance measures are also added here.

Now, assume the SVM classifier has the form (3), and an arbitrary kernel function $K(x, x') = \phi(x)^\top \phi(x')$ is used instead of the linear one. See e.g. [9, 18, 19, 20] for details. Although formally similar, the case of an arbitrary kernel K implies that, if an FS procedure as (P1) is desired, nonlinear constraints are involved and thus the optimization problem is harder to solve. For this reason, instead of coping with such hard problem, we propose an alternative strategy: first, (P1) is solved (as before), and then the SVM classifier (with the selected kernel) is built, using only the features selected in the problem described in Section 2.1. In what follows we focus on the radial kernel, even though one can consider any arbitrary kernel K . First, we define the binary variables z identifying the features which are selected for classifying. The choice of the features, identified with the vector z , leads to the kernel K_z , defined as

$$K_z(x, x') = \exp \left(-\gamma \left(\sum_{k=1}^N z_k (x^{(k)} - x'^{(k)})^2 \right) \right),$$

130 where $x^{(k)}$ denotes the k -th component of vector x .

For z (and thus K_z) fixed, the aim is to solve (4), but replacing the terms $\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{w}$ and $\mathbf{w}^\top \phi(x_i)$, respectively, by the expressions (6) and (7), apart from adding the constraints related to the performance measurements, as described in [31]. Therefore, the cost-sensitive sparse SVM with an arbitrary kernel K is defined (once z is fixed) as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\alpha, \xi, \beta, \zeta, z} \quad \sum_{i, j \in I} \alpha_i y_i \alpha_j y_j K_z(x_i, x_j) + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\
& \text{s.t.} \quad y_i (\sum_{j \in I} \alpha_j y_j K_z(x_i, x_j) + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad \forall i \in I \\
& \quad \quad 0 \leq \xi_i \leq M(1 - \zeta_i) \quad \forall i \in I \\
& \quad \quad \sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i = 0 \\
& \quad \quad 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C/2 \quad \forall i \in I \quad (P3) \\
& \quad \quad \sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i (1 - y_i) \geq \lambda_{-1}^* \sum_{i \in I} (1 - y_i) \\
& \quad \quad \sum_{i \in I} \zeta_i (1 + y_i) \geq \lambda_1^* \sum_{i \in I} (1 + y_i) \\
& \quad \quad \zeta_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in I
\end{aligned}$$

Let us discuss the formulation (P3). The set of features is fixed through z . The objective function, the first, third and fourth constraints are the usual ones in SVM. The second constraint together with the fifth, sixth and seventh constraints force some samples to be correctly classified, as in (P1).

3. Experiment Description

In this section, the solutions of the cost-sensitive sparse SVM with linear kernel (problem (P2)) are compared to those under the radial kernel (problem (P3)), where, as it was described in the previous section, the variables z in both (P2) and (P3) are the solutions of the FS problem formulated by (P1). Also, the solutions under the sparse methodology will be tested against the standard linear SVM. Although it would be natural to compare the solutions of (P3) with the solutions of a standard radial SVM, this comparison is not straightforward since (P1) may become infeasible when the performance measures obtained with the radial SVM are higher than those under the linear SVM.

Next, a description of how the experiments have been carried out is given. In order to solve problems (*P1*), (*P2*) and (*P3*), the solver Gurobi, [36], and its Python language interface, [37], are used. In order to implement these FS procedures, a 10-fold cross-validation (CV), [38], is used. Also, depending on
155 whether the linear or the radial kernel is considered, a parameter C or a pair of parameters (C, γ) must be tuned. Hence, in either the first or in the second case, $C = \gamma = \{2^{-5}, 2^{-4}, \dots, 2^4, 2^5\}$ are considered. In addition, a time limit of 300 seconds is set, giving the solver enough time for finding (sub)optimal solutions. Parameters M and L are set as 100. Finally, in order to get the best set of
160 parameters, another 10-fold CV is carried out and the best set of parameters selected is the one with highest accuracy in average.

For a better understanding, the whole procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1.

4. Numerical Results

Here, the experimental results are presented. We have chosen the datasets
165 `wisconsin` (Breast Cancer Wisconsin (Diagnostic) Data Set), `votes` (Congressional Voting Records Data Set), `nursery` (Nursery Data Set), `Australian` (Statlog (Australian Credit Approval) Data Set) and `careval` (Car Evaluation Data Set), all well referenced and described with detail in [39]. First, a brief
170 data description is given in Section 4.1. Then, results under the linear kernel approach will be presented and discussed in Section 4.2. Finally, the case of the radial kernel will be analyzed in Section 4.3.

Note that the main idea of a FS approach is to reduce the number of features in such a way that the performance is not too affected. As we can control
175 the proportion of samples well classified, this is not a problematic issue. In fact, experiments are done so that new performance measurements will not be 0.025 points lower than the originals (those obtained under the standard version of the SVM with linear kernel). Using the notation as in [31] (where

Algorithm 1: Pseudocode for general kernel approach.

```

1 for  $kf = 1, \dots, folds$  do
2   Split data ( $D$ ) into “folds” subsets,  $D = \{D_1, \dots, D_{folds}\}$ 
3   Set  $Validation = D_{kf}$  and set  $I = D - \{D_{kf}\}$ 
4   for each pair ( $C, gamma$ ) do
5     for  $kf2 = 1, \dots, folds2$  do
6       split  $D' = D - \{D_{kf}\}$  into “folds2” subsets,
7          $D' = \{D'_1, \dots, D'_{folds2}\}$ 
8       Set  $Validation' = D'_{kf2}$  and set  $I' = D' - \{D_{kf2}\}$ 
9       Run ( $P1$ ) over  $I$ , and select the relevant features.
10      Run ( $P2$ ) or ( $P3$ ) over  $I$  with the corresponding modified
11      kernel.
12      Validate over  $Validation'$ , getting the accuracy ( $acc[kf2]$ )
13    end
14    Calculate the average accuracies  $(\sum_{kf2} acc[kf2])/folds2$ 
15    if  $acc[kf2] \geq bestacc$  then
16      | Set  $bestacc = acc[kf2]$ ,  $bestgamma = gamma$  and  $bestC = C$ 
17    end
18  end
19  Run ( $P1$ ) over  $I$ , and select the relevant features.
20  Run ( $P2$ ) or ( $P3$ ) with the corresponding modified kernel and the
21  parameters  $bestgamma$  and  $bestC$ , using  $I$ .
22  Validate over  $Validation$ , getting the accuracy ( $acc2[kf]$ ), and the
23  correct classification probabilities ( $TPR[kf]$ ,  $TNR[kf]$ ) as well as
24  the number of features selected  $Z[kf] = \sum_{k=1}^N z[k]$ .
25 end
26 Calculate and display the average performance measures:
27  $(\sum_{kf} acc2[kf])/folds$ ,  $(\sum_{kf} TPR[kf])/folds$ ,  $(\sum_{kf} TNR[kf])/folds$ 
28 and  $(\sum_{kf} Z[kf])/folds$ 

```

TNR and TPR are the true negative and true positive rates, and TNR_0 and TPR_0 are their obtained values under the standard SVM with linear kernel on a validation sample), $TNR \geq \lambda_{-1} = \min\{1, TNR_0 - 0.025\}$ and $TPR \geq \lambda_1 = \min\{1, TPR_0 - 0.025\}$ are desired. For both linear and radial cases we have considered the two possible selection of the thresholds, defined by (10) and (11).

4.1. Data description

The performance of these novel approaches is illustrated using five real-life datasets from the UCI Repository, [39]. Positive label will be assigned to the majority class in 2-class datasets. In addition, multiclass datasets are transformed into 2-class ones, by giving positive label to the largest class and negative labels to the remaining samples. Also, categorical variables are transformed into dummy variables, i.e, if a categorical variable with ν levels is present, it will be replaced by $\nu - 1$ binary variables. A description of the datasets can be found in Table 1. Such table is split in 4 columns. The first shows the name of the dataset. The total number of samples of the dataset is given in the second one. The number of variables considered, and the number (and percentage) of positive samples in the dataset, are given in the two last columns.

Name	$ \Omega $	V	$ \Omega_+ $ (%)
wisconsin	569	30	357 (62.7 %)
votes	435	32	267 (61.4 %)
nursery	12960	19	4320 (33.3 %)
Australian	690	34	383 (55.5 %)
careval	1728	15	1210 (70.023 %)

Table 1: Details concerning the implementation of the CSVM for the considered datasets.

4.2. Results under the cost-sensitive sparse SVM with linear kernel

As commented before, two types of results will be shown here, as in the following subsection. The first one will correspond to the results when Hoeffding

200 Inequality is not considered (10), whereas the other one consists on the values obtained when Hoeffding is used (11). The results will show how the first option leads to more sparsity while the second choice implies a better predictive power. Let us start with the first case, summarized in Table 2.

The first column of Table 2 gives the name of the dataset used. Then, the
205 second and third columns show, respectively, the performance measures for the standard SVM (using the linear kernel) and the proposed cost-sensitive sparse methodology. Such columns are split into two subcolumns: the first one shows the average values and the second one the standard deviations. The last column reports the feature reduction, by indicating the original and selected (average)
210 number of variables. From the table, it can be concluded that the approach with a linear kernel works well in general. In the case of `wisconsin`, the TPR has desirable values, since it only differentiates -0.019 points from the original. However, in the case of the accuracy and TNR, the loss is bigger than 0.025 points. This is due mainly to two aspects: first, the constraints are forced
215 for the training sample while the performance is calculated using a validation sample. Second, since the thresholds are considered as $\lambda_1^* = \lambda_1$, $\lambda_{-1}^* = \lambda_{-1}$, this implies we are not much restrictive as if $\lambda_1^* > \lambda_1$ ($\lambda_{-1}^* > \lambda_{-1}$) were required. Nevertheless, the new TNR value is only 0.038 points smaller than the original, and the reduction of features is significant since only two variables out of 30 are
220 used. Also, in `votes` the features are significantly reduced and the most affected performance measure is the TPR, which decreases 0.027 points, which makes the accuracy smaller. However, the value on the TNR is increased. As happened with `wisconsin`, the loss is due mainly to the two facts previously mentioned. For `nursery`, an amazing reduction to only one feature is achieved, in addition
225 getting a perfect classification. This is explained as follows. As commented in Section 4.1, multiclass datasets are transformed into 2-class ones, and this is the case, obtaining the classes “`not_recom`” and “`others`”, which are the positive and negative classes, respectively. In addition, one of the (categorical) features in the data (which is the one selected by our procedure) completely determines
230 the class. In `Australian`, the total number of variables is also reduced to only

Table 2: Performance measures under the cost-sensitive sparse SVM with linear kernel and $\lambda_1^* = \lambda_1, \lambda_{-1}^* = \lambda_{-1}$.

Name		SVM		FS		Feature reduction
		Mean	Std	Mean	Std	
wisconsin	Acc	0.975	0.021	0.947	0.025	30 \rightarrow 2 (0 Std)
	TPR	0.992	0.013	0.973	0.031	
	TNR	0.943	0.051	0.905	0.063	
votes	Acc	0.954	0.033	0.949	0.036	32 \rightarrow 2 (0 Std)
	TPR	0.955	0.038	0.928	0.059	
	TNR	0.947	0.059	0.979	0.036	
nursery	Acc	1	0	1	0	19 \rightarrow 1 (0 Std)
	TPR	1	0	1	0	
	TNR	1	0	1	0	
Australian	Acc	0.848	0.051	0.855	0.057	34 \rightarrow 1 (0 Std)
	TPR	0.798	0.083	0.801	0.087	
	TNR	0.912	0.05	0.926	0.041	
careval	Acc	0.956	0.017	0.946	0.019	15 \rightarrow 9 (0 Std)
	TPR	0.96	0.022	0.963	0.017	
	TNR	0.948	0.024	0.907	0.04	

Table 3: Performance measures under the cost-sensitive sparse SVM with linear kernel and $\lambda_1^* = \lambda_1 + \sqrt{-\log \alpha / (2|I_1|)}$, $\lambda_{-1}^* = \lambda_{-1} + \sqrt{-\log \alpha / (2|I_{-1}|)}$.

Name		SVM		FS		Feature reduction
		Mean	Std	Mean	Std	
wisconsin	Acc	0.975	0.021	0.965	0.023	30 \rightarrow 6.2 (0.919 Std)
	TPR	0.992	0.013	0.975	0.023	
	TNR	0.943	0.051	0.947	0.048	
votes	Acc	0.954	0.033	0.954	0.033	32 \rightarrow 9.3 (1.16 Std)
	TPR	0.955	0.038	0.96	0.034	
	TNR	0.947	0.059	0.945	0.052	
nursery	Acc	1	0	1	0	19 \rightarrow 1 (0 Std)
	TPR	1	0	1	0	
	TNR	1	0	1	0	
Australian	Acc	0.848	0.051	0.837	0.057	34 \rightarrow 5.75 (1.89 Std)
	TPR	0.769	0.083	0.772	0.074	
	TNR	0.912	0.05	0.924	0.053	
careval	Acc	0.956	0.017	0.954	0.018	15 \rightarrow 11 (0 Std)
	TPR	0.96	0.022	0.962	0.018	
	TNR	0.948	0.024	0.935	0.039	

one, having similar performance measures values as in the standard SVM. In fact, we obtain here even better results than under the original linear SVM. If the variable selected with the algorithm is studied, one can observe that it is a binary variable X , where the contingency table together with the class variable is Table 4. Hence this variable is by itself a good predictor, as the FS procedure pointed out. In the case of `careval`, we got the smallest reduction in the number of variables selected, maintaining the performance measures values above the imposed thresholds.

	X = 0	X = 1
Class +	306	77
Class -	23	284

Table 4: Contingency table of the feature selected in `Australian`.

Consider next the results shown by Table 3, for the case where we are restrictive regarding the performance values, that is, when $\lambda_1^* = \lambda_1 + \sqrt{-\log \alpha / (2|I_1|)}$ and $\lambda_{-1}^* = \lambda_{-1} + \sqrt{-\log \alpha / (2|I_{-1}|)}$. From the table, it can be seen how this approach works better concerning the performance measures, but achieves less sparse solutions. For example, if we focus on `wisconsin`, as much the TNR as the TPR and the accuracy, obtain the desired performance requirements. However, only a reduction of variables of a fifth part is obtained. In the case of `votes`, an analogous result is obtained for the performance measures and only a reduction in a third part of the variables is achieved. The same pattern as before is observed for `nursery`. For `Australian`, we obtain even an improvement in all the three performance measures considered, reducing the number of features to a fifth part. Finally, we get again in `careval` the smallest reduction in the number of variables selected, maintaining the performance measures values above the thresholds imposed as before, but using a larger number of features.

4.3. Results under the cost-sensitive sparse SVM with radial kernel

The analogous results to those in Section 4.2 are presented here, for the case of the radial kernel. However, only `wisconsin`, `votes` and `Australian`

datasets are used here. As shown by Tables 5 and 6 and similarly as occurred in Section 4.2, the use of the threshold values obtained by the Hoeffding inequality (as in (11)) lead to a lower level of sparsity, but also, to a higher predictive power in general (particularly, when achieving the desired bounds). Concerning the performance measures, it can be deduced from Tables 5 and 6 that this approach works well in general, especially when using Hoeffding. Finally, it should be noted how the reduction in the number of features is quite notable for some datasets, as before.

Table 5: Performance measures under the cost-sensitive sparse SVM with radial kernel and $\lambda_1^* = \lambda_1, \lambda_{-1}^* = \lambda_{-1}$.

Name	SVM		FS		Feature reduction	
	Mean	Std	Mean	Std		
wisconsin	Acc	0.975	0.021	0.956	0.012	30 → 2 (0 Std)
	TPR	0.992	0.013	0.988	0.016	
	TNR	0.943	0.051	0.893	0.051	
votes	Acc	0.954	0.033	0.947	0.034	32 → 2 (0 Std)
	TPR	0.955	0.038	0.928	0.059	
	TNR	0.947	0.059	0.974	0.036	
nursery	Acc	1	0	1	0	19 → 1 (0 Std)
	TPR	1	0	1	0	
	TNR	1	0	1	0	

Table 6: Performance measures under the cost-sensitive sparse SVM with radial kernel and $\lambda_1^* = \lambda_1 + \sqrt{-\log \alpha / (2|I_1|)}$, $\lambda_{-1}^* = \lambda_{-1} + \sqrt{-\log \alpha / (2|I_{-1}|)}$.

Name	SVM		FS		Feature reduction	
	Mean	Std	Mean	Std		
wisconsin	Acc	0.975	0.021	0.947	0.03	30 \rightarrow 6.2 (0.919 Std)
	TPR	0.992	0.013	0.967	0.039	
	TNR	0.943	0.051	0.907	0.02	
votes	Acc	0.954	0.033	0.949	0.03	32 \rightarrow 9.3 (1.16 Std)
	TPR	0.955	0.038	0.959	0.034	
	TNR	0.947	0.059	0.939	0.043	
nursery	Acc	1	0	1	0	19 \rightarrow 1 (0 Std)
	TPR	1	0	1	0	
	TNR	1	0	1	0	

5. Concluding remarks

265 In this paper we have proposed a Feature Selection procedure for binary
Support Vector Machines that yields a novel, sparse, SVM. Contrary to existing
Feature Selection approaches, we take explicitly into account that misclassifica-
tion costs may be rather different in the two groups, and thus, instead of seeking
the classifier maximizing the margin, we seek the most sparse classifier that at-
270 tains certain true positive and true negative rates on the dataset. For both
SVM with linear and radial kernel, the problem is written in a straightforward
manner, solving first a mixed integer linear problem and then their standard
SVM formulations, considering only the features obtained in the first problem
as well as the performance constraints. The reported numerical results show
275 that the novel approaches lead to comparable or better performance rates in
addition to an important reduction in the number of variables.

Several extensions of the approach presented in this paper are possible and,
in our opinion, deserve further study. First, several classification and regression
procedures based on optimization problems, such as Support Vector Regres-
280 sion, logistic regression or distance-weighted discrimination, are amenable to
address, as done here, an integrated FS and classification or regression. The
optimization problems obtained in this way have a structure which should be
exploited to make the approach competitive. Second, even within SVM, it
should be observed that SVM is a tool for binary classification. For multiclass
285 datasets, classification is performed by solving a series of SVM problems, see
[18, 40]. When some classes are hard to identify, the basic multiclass strategies
may yield discouraging results. Performing simultaneously feature selection and
class fusion, as in [41], is an interesting nontrivial extension of our approach. To
do this, problems (P1), (P2) and (P3) will need to be conveniently modified.

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295 Appendix

In this section we describe step by step how formulation (9) is built from equation (8). Hence, let us suppose first that we have the model

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_{\mathbf{w}, \beta, \xi} \quad & \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{w} + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\
\text{s.t.} \quad & y_i(\mathbf{w}^\top x_i + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad i \in I \\
& 0 \leq \xi_i \leq L(1 - \zeta_i) \quad i \in I \\
& \mu(\zeta)_\ell \geq \lambda_\ell \quad \ell \in L \\
& \zeta_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad i \in I.
\end{aligned}$$

This one can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_{\zeta} \quad & \min_{\mathbf{w}, \beta, \xi} \quad \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{w} + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\
\text{s.t.} \quad & \zeta_i \in \{0, 1\} \quad i \in I \quad \text{s.t.} \quad y_i(\mathbf{w}^\top x_i + \beta) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \quad i \in I \\
& \mu(\zeta)_\ell \geq \lambda_\ell \quad \ell \in L \quad \text{s.t.} \quad 0 \leq \xi_i \leq L(1 - \zeta_i) \quad i \in I
\end{aligned}$$

If we assume that the binary variables ζ fixed, the Karush–Kuhn–Tucker (KKT) conditions for the inner problem are

$$\begin{aligned}
\omega &= \sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i x_i \\
0 &= \sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i \\
0 &\leq \alpha_i \leq C/2 \quad i \in I.
\end{aligned}$$

300 Substituting these expressions into the last optimization problem, the partial dual of such problem can be calculated, obtaining

$$\begin{aligned}
\min_{\zeta} \quad & \min_{\alpha, \beta, \xi} \quad \left(\sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i x_i \right)^\top \left(\sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i x_i \right) + C \sum_{i \in I} \xi_i \\
\text{s.t.} \quad & z_j \in \{0, 1\} \quad j \in J \quad \text{s.t.} \quad y_i \left(\left(\sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i x_i \right)^\top x_i + \beta \right) \geq 1 - \xi_i \quad i \in I \\
& \mu(\zeta)_\ell \geq \lambda_\ell \quad \ell \in L \quad 0 \leq \xi_i \leq L(1 - \zeta_i) \quad i \in I \\
& \sum_{i \in I} \alpha_i y_i = 0 \\
& 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C/2 \quad i \in I
\end{aligned}$$

As a last step, the kernel trick is used and the final formulation (9) is obtained.

References

- [1] D. Bertsimas, A. K. O’Hair, W. R. Pulleyblank, *The Analytics Edge*, Dynamic Ideas, Massachusetts, 2016.
- 305 [2] F. Provost, T. Fawcett, *Data Science for Business: What You Need to Know about Data Mining and Data-Analytic Thinking*, 1st Edition, O’Reilly Media, Inc., 2013.
- [3] P. L. Bartlett, M. I. Jordan, J. D. McAuliffe, Convexity, classification, and risk bounds, *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 101 (473)
310 (2006) 138–156.
- [4] A. Ben-Tal, S. Bhadra, C. Bhattacharyya, J. Saketha Nath, Chance constrained uncertain classification via robust optimization, *Mathematical Programming* 127 (1) (2011) 145–173.
- [5] R. I. Boç, N. Lorenz, Optimization problems in statistical learning: Duality and optimality conditions, *European Journal of Operational Research*
315 213 (2) (2011) 395–404.
- [6] P. S. Bradley, U. M. Fayyad, O. L. Mangasarian, *Mathematical Programming for Data Mining: Formulations and Challenges*, *INFORMS Journal on Computing* 11 (3) (1999) 217–238.
- 320 [7] E. Carrizosa, A. Nogales-Gómez, D. Romero-Morales, Strongly agree or strongly disagree?: Rating features in support vector machines, *Information Sciences* 329 (2016) 256–273.
- [8] E. Carrizosa, A. Nogales-Gómez, D. Romero-Morales, Clustering categories in support vector machines, *Omega* 66 (2017) 28–37.
- 325 [9] E. Carrizosa, D. Romero-Morales, Supervised classification and mathematical optimization, *Computers & Operations Research* 40 (1) (2013) 150–165.

- [10] D. Corne, C. Dhaenens, L. Jourdan, Synergies between operations research and data mining: The emerging use of multi-objective approaches, *European Journal of Operational Research* 221 (3) (2012) 469–479.
- 330 [11] J. S. Marron, M. J. Todd, J. Ahn, Distance-weighted discrimination, *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 102 (480) (2007) 1267–1271.
- [12] S. Meisel, D. Mattfeld, Synergies of Operations Research and Data Mining, *European Journal of Operational Research* 206 (1) (2010) 1–10.
- [13] O. P. Panagopoulos, V. Pappu, P. Xanthopoulos, P. M. Pardalos, Con-
335 strained subspace classifier for high dimensional datasets, *Omega* 59 (2016) 40–46.
- [14] F. Plastria, E. Carrizosa, Minmax-distance approximation and separation problems: geometrical properties, *Mathematical Programming* 132 (1) (2012) 153–177.
- 340 [15] P. Richtárik, M. Takáč, Parallel coordinate descent methods for big data optimization, *Mathematical Programming* 156 (1) (2016) 433–484.
- [16] B. N. Sánchez, M. Wu, P. X. K. Song, W. Wang, Study design in high-dimensional classification analysis, *Biostatistics* 17 (4) (2016) 722. doi: 10.1093/biostatistics/kxw018.
- 345 [17] X. Shen, G. C. Tseng, X. Zhang, W. H. Wong, On ψ -learning, *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 98 (463) (2003) 724–734.
- [18] N. Cristianini, J. Shawe-Taylor, *An Introduction to Support Vector Machines and Other Kernel-based Learning Methods*, Cambridge University Press, 2000.
- 350 [19] V. Vapnik, *The Nature of Statistical Learning Theory*, Springer-Verlag New York, Inc., New York, NY, USA, 1995.
- [20] V. Vapnik, *Statistical learning theory*, Vol. 1, Wiley New York, 1998.

- [21] H. Aytug, Feature selection for support vector machines using Generalized Benders Decomposition, *European Journal of Operational Research* 244 (1) (2015) 210–218.
- [22] P. Bertolazzi, G. Felici, P. Festa, G. Fiscon, E. Weitschek, Integer programming models for feature selection: New extensions and a randomized solution algorithm, *European Journal of Operational Research* 250 (2) (2016) 389–399.
- [23] P. S. Bradley, O. L. Mangasarian, W. N. Street, Feature Selection via Mathematical Programming, *INFORMS Journal on Computing* 10 (2) (1998) 209–217.
- [24] E. Carrizosa, B. Martín-Barragán, D. Romero-Morales, Detecting relevant variables and interactions in supervised classification, *European Journal of Operational Research* 213 (1) (2011) 260–269.
- [25] G. M. Fung, O. L. Mangasarian, A Feature Selection Newton Method for Support Vector Machine Classification, *Computational Optimization and Applications* 28 (2) (2004) 185–202. doi:10.1023/B:COAP.0000026884.66338.df.
URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1023/B:COAP.0000026884.66338.df>
- [26] I. Guyon, A. Elisseeff, An Introduction to Variable and Feature Selection, *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 3 (Mar) (2003) 1157–1182.
- [27] H. A. Le Thi, H. M. Le, T. P. Dinh, Feature selection in machine learning: an exact penalty approach using a Difference of Convex function Algorithm, *Machine Learning* 101 (1) (2015) 163–186.
- [28] S. Maldonado, R. Weber, A wrapper method for feature selection using Support Vector Machines, *Information Sciences* 179 (13) (2009) 2208–2217.
- [29] S. Maldonado, R. Weber, J. Basak, Simultaneous feature selection and classification using kernel-penalized support vector machines, *Information Sciences* 181 (1) (2011) 115–128.

- [30] J. Weston, S. Mukherjee, O. Chapelle, M. Pontil, T. Poggio, V. Vapnik, Feature Selection for SVMs, in: T. K. Leen, T. G. Dietterich, V. Tresp (Eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 13*, MIT Press, 2001, pp. 668–674.
385 URL <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/1850-feature-selection-for-svms.pdf>
- [31] S. Benítez-Peña, R. Blanquero, E. Carrizosa, P. Ramírez-Cobo, On Support Vector Machines under a multiple-cost scenario, working Paper (2017).
- [32] D. Bertsimas, A. King, R. Mazumder, et al., Best subset selection via a
390 modern optimization lens, *The Annals of Statistics* 44 (2) (2016) 813–852.
- [33] D. Bertsimas, R. Mazumder, et al., Least quantile regression via modern optimization, *The Annals of Statistics* 42 (6) (2014) 2494–2525.
- [34] E. Carrizosa, A. V. Olivares-Nadal, P. Ramírez-Cobo, A sparsity-controlled vector autoregressive model, *Biostatistics* (2017) kxw042.
- 395 [35] E. Carrizosa, B. Martín-Barragán, D. Romero-Morales, Multi-group support vector machines with measurement costs: A biobjective approach, *Discrete Applied Mathematics* 156 (6) (2008) 950–966.
- [36] Gurobi Optimization, Inc., *Gurobi optimizer reference manual* (2016).
URL <http://www.gurobi.com>
- 400 [37] Python Core Team, *Python: A dynamic, open source programming language*, Python Software Foundation. (2015).
URL <https://www.python.org>
- [38] R. Kohavi, A Study of Cross-Validation and Bootstrap for Accuracy Estimation and Model Selection, in: *IJCAI*, Vol. 14, Stanford, CA, 1995, pp.
405 1137–1143.
- [39] M. Lichman, *UCI Machine Learning Repository* (2013).
URL <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml>

- [40] L. Wang, X. Shen, On L1-Norm Multiclass Support Vector Machines, *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 102 (478) (2007) 583–594.
doi:10.1198/016214506000001383.
- 410
- [41] J. Guo, Simultaneous variable selection and class fusion for high-dimensional linear discriminant analysis, *Biostatistics* 11 (4) (2010) 599.
doi:10.1093/biostatistics/kxq023.